

Original Article

Factors Affecting the Choice of Transport Enterprises: Case Study of Import-Export Enterprises in Danang

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Abstract

Selecting transport enterprises is always a difficult stage for every import-export company. It plays an important role in determining the success of one or more shipments. The purpose of this study is to find out the factors that may impact on the decision of selecting transport enterprises and through that give suitable solutions. In this study, the authors have used qualitative methods, quantitative methods. The targets for the survey are the businesses that participate in the import-export industry in Danang. By using these data analyses: Cronbach's Alpha, EFA, Correlation, and Regression, the results show that there are 2 factors: Relationship and Strength that have an impact on the selection. In which Relationship criteria is considered as the most important factor. This study is based on the real problem of the import-export enterprises to help them realise that the relationship between 2 parties are really important for the current or further cooperation, and what are the things the transport enterprises should improve to have a competitive advantage.

Keywords: Case study, Danang, Import-export, Relationship, Transport enterprises

1. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, with the outstanding development of countries in the World and new opportunities are opened for developing countries. Vietnam has been gradually integrating through free trade agreements (FTAs) and international trade. Opening up huge opportunities for the domestic economy, to exchange, learn and work with developed countries to help Vietnam's economy change positively (baochinhphu.vn, 2022). With the development of the economy, the activities of goods exchange or transportation have gradually transformed into an essential need in business activities, and Logistics has become a highly competitive market in recent years. Therefore, the number of businesses operating in this field is also increasing day by day, specifically with about

4000-4500 businesses providing this service and up to 30,000 companies related to the industry. According to the report, in 2019 Vietnam's total import and export turnover reached 517.26 billion USD and in 2020 reached 545.36 billion USD. These results make Vietnam's trade balance still maintained and developed. Especially Da Nang city, which is a dynamic city, is attracting a large amount of investment from abroad. With the advantage of being located on the East coast with the Han River estuary and its port located in an important position, it is identified as the East-West economic corridor.

So that Da Nang is having a great advantage for logistics businesses to operate and develop. According to the announcement of the Ministry of Industry and Trade, Da Nang has 12 enterprises named in the 315 "Reputable export enterprises"

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of Vietnam, an increase of more than 3 units compared to the number in 2019. In addition, the “People’s Committee of Da Nang City” has also coordinated with the “American Agency for International Development” (USAID) to conduct the project “Trade Facilitation” to simplify the procedures, customs clearance papers, reducing time and costs for businesses.

Currently, domestic enterprises, especially those providing logistics services, are facing certain difficulties such as the COVID Epidemic, the company’s business situation, etc. With regard to the COVID Epidemic, the industry has suffered a serious impact when many factories have had to suspend operations, resulting in a lot of goods being stored while the goods being shipped are few but there is a lot of storage. And with the current stressful epidemic situation around the world, countries are also restricting the movement of goods both at home and abroad.

That makes it really difficult for shipping businesses to run their business. In addition, for business activities of enterprises in the epidemic situation, they must also consider carefully when choosing transport partners when the logistics cost of carrier foreign enterprises has not decreased but also increased very high. This fact seriously affects the supply chain activities of businesses in Vietnam a lot. For this topic, previous studies have been carried out on the subjects of small businesses, those who directly transport or just stop at the study of factors. There is still no research targeting import-export enterprises. Therefore, this article is conducted with the aim of determining the factors affecting the selection of transport enterprises in the case of import-export enterprises in Danang city.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Consumer Behaviour Theory

The theory of consumer behaviour shows the overall decisions of consumers for activities of acquiring, consuming, and discarding goods, including products and services, activities and ideas, by decision-making units (people) over time (Nguyen Xuan et al., 2011). In short, the theory of consumer behaviour is much broader than the mere concept of buying. Through the theory of consumer behaviour, consumers’ decisions will be more rational through the rational budget allocation to maximise their satisfaction and benefits (Nguyen Xuan et al., 2011). The study of customer behaviour is really important to understand and know why customers want to buy a certain product or

service (Nguyen Thuy, 2014). Take that as a basis to give criteria or factors to choose a transport service provider.

Factors Affecting Choice of Transport Enterprises

Reliability

Service reliability indicates the service provider’s ability to meet and fulfil commitments and is considered as the most important factor in choosing a transport provider. According to the analysis of Barthel et al. (2010) “Reliability” can be defined as on-time delivery compared to the promised time by the shipping line. Coulter et al. (1989) define “Reliability” as a factor that measures the shipper values “precision” or carrier’s reliability and say that the shipper competing for the business of any segment high on this dimension must create a “Reliable” image. According to the result of the master thesis (Nguyen Thuy, 2014) confirmed that the factor “Reliability” played the most important part when choosing the transport brand. And the study suggests that the shipping carriers should have priority policies in lifting high reliability of transportation services to attract new customers as well as retain existing ones.

Parampal Singh & Deepinder S. Garcha conclude that reliable pick-up service and reliable transit time are also important elements while choosing a transportation provider (Singh & Garcha, 1995). According to the conclusion of Michael A. McGinnis, the result also shows that speed & reliability is almost the top essential factor for shippers while selecting a carrier. The result also suggests that those researchers in this area of choosing freight transportation and physical distribution management should consider while concluding just upon the ranks of variables without paying attention to their relative importance (McGinnis, 1979).

H1: Reliability has a positive effect on the choice of the transport enterprise.

Risk Avoidance

Risk prevention is understood as the elimination of possible risks that affect the business activities of enterprises. In transportation, the risk is an important issue in the orientation of a good’s owner (Coulter et al., 1989). Risk avoidance in some studies of other authors can also be named as security/ control factor. According to Coulter et al (1989), if a firm selects a market segment comprised of firms high on this factor, it should position itself as

providing low-risk for its customers. Besides, they also think that buyers need to be assured that their shipment will arrive safely and on time (Coulter et al., 1989).

The conclusion of Roberts (2012) mentions that even this factor is no longer important to consider for most of the participants in carrier selection. This criterion is also an important one due to the fact that not all goods shipped are of the same type. Its importance depends on which type of shipped products. If the shipped goods are fragile and highly hazardous, this criterion will be very necessary. Or if the shipped products are canned or covered, it will be least important as well (Roberts, 2012).

H2: Risk avoidance has a positive effect on the choice of the transport enterprise.

Customer Service

Expressed through the quality of sales staff, receiving and delivering goods in sufficient quantity and quality assurance (Coulter et al., 1989). Coulter et al. (1989) also emphasise the importance of customer service and to increase work efficiency, employees need to be rewarded based on creativity in ideas and work. According to Kannan et al. (2011), the selection of carriers always faced a trade-off between multiple criteria. In this study, Kannan et al. conclude that shippers always want to receive a better service at a competitive rate and they are not willing to compromise under service or rate. Even though the result shows that rate is of the top importance, it does not mean the service factor is not a competitive criterion for them. It just means that the service factor will be considered after they reach the rate objectives (Kannan et al., 2011).

The result of Kumar & Rajan (2002) at the first level of hierarchy shows that the customer service criteria were found to be the least important factor and the cost issues factor is the most important factor that should be considered (Kumar & Rajan, 2002). The study of D'Este & Meyrick (1992) shows that the following factors: price, quality of service, speed and reliability are still the most important factors. The result mainly highlights the theorist's misconceptions that the economic paradigm of short-term cost minimization can not be used to explain the shipper's behaviour (D'Este & Meyrick, 1992).

The findings in this study, especially the used factors of Wong et al. (2008) show us the importance and usefulness of each criterion to transport enterprises when their services are deployed in the port of Southern China. Moreover,

the local transport provider can also gain benefit from these findings, which help them enhance their service sectors to meet the expectation of shippers in the PRD region (Wong et al., 2008).

H3: Customer service has a positive effect on the choice of the transport enterprise.

Cost

Cost is defined as a cost or price that the carrier charges upon their providing transport services (Singh & Garcha, 1995). Another definition of (Nguyen Thuy, 2014) is that transportation cost includes freight charges and additional charges attached to the freight (Nguyen Thuy, 2014). In addition, there are many other ways to call the cost criteria in another study such as price factor, rate. According to the result of Solakivi & Ojala (2017) shows that those firms that emphasise business cost in their strategic value the cost determinants of transport selection are higher than those firms with less emphasis. The research also finds that the use of the 5-point Likert scale for the study of carrier selection is no longer effective (Solakivi & Ojala, 2017).

As I mentioned in the above factor of customer service, the result of Kannan et al. (2011) shows that rate is the most important factor in their study about the ocean carrier selection and it also involves the trade-off (Kannan et al., 2011). According to the research of Kumar & Rajan (2002), the cost issues take place in the top most important factor followed by the transit time and qualitative issues. The research uses the AHP analysis to conclude that the cost criteria are the most important consideration among the survey respondents (Kumar & Rajan, 2002).

The study of D'Este & Meyrick (1992) reminds us that the price factor is one of the most important elements when researching which factor affects the choice of the carrier (D'Este & Meyrick, 1992). According to the thesis of (Nguyen Thuy, 2014), the transportation cost is the second element that affects the selection of carriers and also mentioned that this factor is even an important factor but it does not a priority that affects the decision of choosing transport enterprises upon the study of Tuna (2002) and Rotaris (2012) (Nguyen Thuy, 2014). Through the study of McGinnis (1979), the research concludes that freight rates factor is just ranked later speed and reliability factor, and freight rates criteria is the one of three-factor highly necessary when choosing the transport enterprises (McGinnis, 1979).

Fanam & Ackerly (2019) find that the price factor is less important to Tasmania shippers.

According to the situation that the freight rates in Tasmania are high and there is also a support of the Tasmania freight equalisation, the shippers in Tasmania still do not consider cost as the most essential factor while making a decision on selecting an ocean carrier (Fanam & Ackerly, 2019). According to the finalisation of the Loetveit Pedersen & Gray (1998) study, the survey respondents show that the price factor takes place the most important with other factors by Norwegian exporters. The explanation is that there are extremely high transport costs in Norway. These elements like topography, location, transport distances, and limited local competition can be used to explain the reason for higher costs (Loetveit Pedersen & Gray, 1998).

H4: Cost has a positive effect on the choice of the transport enterprise.

Relationship

This is the unpurposeful factor that I consider to analyse upon the reality and the development

of the logistic industry. The study of Roberts, n.d. supposes that this is an interesting factor that is not the onset of the study (Roberts, n.d. 2012). The research of Nguyen Thuy (2014) also gives the definition through the previous studies of this factor. Wong (2007) defines the relationship between the customers and the carriers as a partnership. Porter (1980) supposes that partnership is a purposeful relationship with the goal to win the competitive advantage in the market. The research of Matear & Gray (1993), Lu (2003), and Wong (2007) point out that the relationship factor is one of the consideration factors while choosing the carrier (Nguyen Thuy, 2014). The questionnaire of this factor will be based on the developed questionnaire of (Nguyen Thuy, 2014) to prove that this factor has a positive impact on the selection of the carrier at the moment.

H5: Relationship has a positive effect on the choice of the transport enterprise.

Fig. 1. Proposed Research Model

3. METHODOLOGY

Research Process Model

Fig. 2. Research Process Model

Qualitative Method

Based on the research information in the Literature Review section, the authors have synthesised criteria and scales that may help the study of this topic. This qualitative research was carried out by focus group interviews. The number of representative interviewers is 5 and Chinh will be a moderator, who will successively consult the invited representatives on the questions proposed in the interview questionnaire. After consulting and reviewing based on the comments of the participants, everyone agreed to combine the two factors, reliability and risk avoidance, and call it

reliability. The designed scales of the two factors at this time will still be kept and combined to measure the reliability factor.

Especially the service quality scale is also through the qualitative method by directly asking a researcher at FPT University who holds a master's degree in economics with business administration. After asking the expert, the recommended scale for the dependent variable would be "Satisfied with transport enterprise". For the other factors, all of the representatives have agreed with these factors and put it into the questionnaire table. So the figure below is the new proposed model after being edited.

Fig. 3. Official Proposed Research Model

Table 1

Official Scales

Factors	Code	Scales	Source
Reliability	T1	Delivering the cargo at the promised time	(McGinnis, 1979)
	T2	Issuing accurate shipping documentation	(Nguyen Thuy, 2014)
	T3	Responding to complaints quickly	(Nguyen Thuy, 2014)
	T4	Low levels of loss and damage	(McGinnis, 1979)
	T5	Ability to monitor the goods in transit	(Loetveit Pedersen & Gray, 1998)
	T6	Knowledge of port/harbour	(Loetveit Pedersen & Gray, 1998)
Customer Service	S1	International distribution/consolidation services	(Coulter et al., 1989)
	S2	Employees' willingness to help customers	(Kannan et al., 2011)
	S3	Giving individual attention to customers	(Kannan et al., 2011)
Cost	C1	Low total shipping costs (freight and surcharges)	(Nguyen Thuy, 2014)
	C2	Competitive rates	(McGinnis, 1979)
	C3	There are specials/discounts available	(Loetveit Pedersen & Gray, 1998)
	C4	Willingness to negotiate rates	(Nguyen Thuy, 2014)
	C5	Rates has long term validity	(Nguyen Thuy, 2014)
Relationship	R1	Gifts from shipping lines.	(Nguyen Thuy, 2014)
	R2	Past cooperation with shipping lines.	(Nguyen Thuy, 2014)
	R3	Have a personal relationship with the shipping line (relatives, friends, etc).	(Nguyen Thuy, 2014)
Selection transport enterprises	Y1	Peace of mind when using the service	(Nguyen Thuy, 2014)
	Y2	Satisfied with transport enterprise	(Trinh Le, 2022)
	Y3	Good shipping rates	(Nguyen Thuy, 2014)
	Y4	Have a good relationship with the transport business	(Nguyen Thuy, 2014)

Quantitative Method

In the quantitative method, the authors have used the SPSS system to analyse based on the collected data. Use Cronbach's alpha tool to analyse the reliability of collected data, continue with the EFA tool to reduce the data, then move to the results with the help of regression and Pearson correlation tool. The authors use the 5 Likert scales to investigate the important level of the proposed factors from (1) is totally disagree to (5) is totally agreed.

Cronbach's Alpha

Cronbach's alpha coefficient is calculated according to the following formula:

$$\alpha = \frac{K}{K-1} \left(1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^K \sigma_{Y_i}^2}{\sigma_X^2} \right)$$

In which:

N: are the number of variables included in the analysis.

$\sigma_{Y_i}^2$: the variance of observed variable i.

σ_X^2 : the variance of the sum variable.

The reliability of the factor will be determined by its α result. If $\alpha \geq 0.9$, it means a very good factor scale. If $0.9 > \alpha \geq 0.8$, it's a good factor scale. If $0.8 > \alpha \geq 0.7$, it's an acceptable factor scale. If $0.7 > \alpha \geq 0.6$, it's an acceptable scale for new studies. If $0.6 > \alpha \geq 0.5$ or $\alpha < 0.5$, it shows that factor scale is not suitable. Furthermore, for the scale to achieve reliability, there are some requirements in the result of this analysis. If Cronbach's alpha ≥ 0.6 , the scale is acceptable in terms of reliability. Moreover, it also requires the total (corrected) variable correlation coefficient ≥ 0.3 .

EFA Analysis

After analysing Cronbach's alpha, the remaining factors are reliable for moving to the next step, which is EFA analysis. EFA is also known as Exploratory Factor Analysis. The purpose of EFA analysis is to reduce data, which helps us more accurately understand the meaning of measured variables. According to Hair & ctg (1998,111), factor loading is an indicator to ensure the practical significance of EFA. It's the relationship between the observed variable and the factor. There are three levels to consider the factor loading: if the result is more than 0.3, factor loading will be considered at the minimum level, if the result is greater than 0.4,

factor loading will be considered as important, if the result is higher than 0.5, factor loading now is considered as practical essential. In addition, the observed variables used in the EFA analysis need to meet the following requirements:

$0.5 \leq KMO \leq 1$, KMO which stands for Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin and is used to determine the sustainability of factor analysis.

Bartlett test < 0.05 and the observed variables are accepted when the total variance $> 50\%$ the coefficient Eigenvalue > 1 .

Pearson Correlation

Pearson correlation coefficient (symbol r) is a test statistic that measures the statistical relationship or association between dependent variables and continuous variables. It (r) fluctuates from -1 to +1. If $r = 0$, there's no linear correlation between the two variables. If $r = 1$, or $r = -1$, there is an absolutely linear relationship. If $r < 0$, it leads to a negative correlation coefficient, which means if x increases, y decreases, and vice. If $r > 0$, it leads to a positive correlation coefficient, which means if x increases, y increases, and vice. Pearson correlation coefficient (r) just to be important if and only if (sig.) $< \alpha = 5\%$. If r is between 0.5 and ± 1 , it means a strong correlation. If r is between 0.3 and ± 0.49 , it has a correlation. If r is less than ± 0.29 , it means a weak correlation. $r = -1$, which means data distributed on a straight line has a negative slope, and $r = 1$, which means data distributed on a straight line has a positive slope.

Regression Analysis

Regression analysis is a statistical technique that helps the researchers be able to estimate the equation that best fits the observed result sets of the dependent and independent variables. Performing linear regression analysis can give researchers the best estimate of the true relationship between variables. Linear regression equation: $y' = \beta x_i + x_i$

Sampling

Sampling Method

The sampling method used in this research will be probability sampling so that the subjects in the survey set have equal opportunities and bring objectivity to the research paper. Specifically, the authors will use simple random sampling for the convenience of research conditions. The

authors will list out all the transport enterprises currently in Da Nang, decide on sample size, then numbering for each sample unit and using the lottery method to choose.

Sample Size

In this study, the authors decided to use the sample size of Tabachnick and Fidell (1996) $80 + 5n$ with $n = 17$ (number of observed variables). Therefore, the expected survey sample size is

165.

4. RESULTS & FINDINGS

The total sample size is 165, which includes 21 questionnaires distributed to 170 import-export businesses in Danang. All survey samples were answered positively and constructively for the research topic.

Characteristics

Table 2

Descriptive statistics of demographic criteria

		Frequency	Percent (%)
Type of business	Joint Stock Company	51	30
	Limited liability company	47	27.6
	Private enterprise	72	42.4
	Total	170	100
Number of employees	Under 500	80	47.1
	500 - 1000	63	37.1
	More than 1000	27	15.9
	Total	170	100
Transaction time	Less than 1 year	15	8.8
	1-3 year	74	43.5
	More than 5 years	81	47.6
	Total	170	100
Types of goods for export	Agricultural products (rice, coffee, pepper, cashew,...)	27	15.9
	Foodstuff, beverage (foodstuff, beverage)	22	12.9
	Machinery and electronic equipment	30	17.6
	Garment products (clothes, shoes)	42	24.7
	Interior and exterior decorations (furniture)	23	13.5
	Frozen seafood, fresh vegetables (cold containers)	26	15.3
	Total	170	100

Assessing the Reliability of Scale (Cronbach's Alpha)

The results showed the items with Cronbach's

Table 3

Summary Cronbach's Alpha coefficients table

No	Items	N of Items	N of Items satisfying	Cronbach'S Alpha
1	Reliability (T)	6	6	0.762
2	Cost (C)	5	5	0.762
3	Relationship (R)	3	3	0.721
4	Selection transport enterprises (Y)	3	3	0.716

coefficient's Alpha are higher than 0.6, which are acceptable factors. The correlation coefficient of variables is also greater than 0.3. There is only one factor Customer service with Cronbach's Alpha less than 0.6, so authors have removed it.

Exploratory Factor Analysis

The results after analysing the EFA contain 14 independent observation variables with the use of Principal method and Varimax rotation.

The results also show Sig. = 0.000, which less than 0.005 is acceptable, and KMO coefficient is 0.866, which is greater than 0.5 is needed. In addition, Eigenvalues result in 1.018 is greater than 1, and the total variance is 56.308 percent >

50%, which means there are 56.308 percent can be explained.

Table 4

Results from independent observation variables

Items	Factor loading		
	1	2	3
C4	0.791		
R1	0.765		
R3	0.697		
C5	0.687		
R2	0.662		
C3	0.636		
T1		0.752	
T4		0.725	
T6		0.724	
T5		0.623	
T3		0.623	
C1			0.809
T2			0.573
C2			0.528
Satisfaction the conditions of coefficients			
Eigenvalue	4.866	1.999	1.018
Cumulative %	56.308%		
KMO	0.866		
Barlett's Test	Sig.=0.000		

After performing EFA analysis for independent observed variables, 14 variables have converged

into 3 groups of new factors named in the table below.

No	Factors	Items	Type
1	Relationship (R)	C4,R1,R3,C5,R2,C3	Independent
2	Reliability (T)	T1,T4,T6,T5,T3	Independent
3	Strengths (S)	C1,T2,C2	Independent

Table 5

The results from dependent variables

Items	Factor loading
	1
Y1	.833
Y2	.797
Y3	.778

Satisfaction the conditions of coefficients

Eigenvalue	1.935
Cumulative %	64.501%
KMO	0.673
Barlett's Test	Sig.=0.000

As the result of analysing EFA of dependent variables, Cronbach's Alpha is 0.716 > 0.6,

Eigenvalue is 1.935 > 1, total variance is 64.501% > 50%, 0.5 < KMO 0.673 < 1, and Barlett's Test

has Sig. = 0.000 < 0.05, which represents all the requirements that are met and can be used in the

next step of study.

Correlation Between Variables

Table 6

Correlations

		X1	X2	X3	Y
X1	Pearson Correlation	1	.318**	.551**	.504**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	170	170	170	170
X2	Pearson Correlation	.318**	1	.446**	.277**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
	N	170	170	170	170
X3	Pearson Correlation	.551**	.446**	1	.478**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
	N	170	170	170	170
Y	Pearson Correlation	.504**	.277**	.478**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	170	170	170	170

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

According to the result of the correlation matrix, with Sig. = 0.000 < 0.05, there is a linear that connects Y dependent variables and independent variables X1, X2, X3. So the linear regression analysis in this case is suitable for use.

Multiple Regression

Table 7

Estimation of beta coefficient by using Enter method

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	1.097	.302		3.634	.000	.501	1.693		
	X1	.372	.083	.345	4.481	.000	.208	.537	.697	1.435
	X3	.327	.087	.289	3.751	.000	.155	.499	.697	1.435

Adjusted R Square = 0.303;

F (ANOVA) = 37.796;

Sig. (ANOVA) = 0.000;

Durbin - Watson = 1.484.

The table of ANOVA analysis results that the statistical F = 37.796 with Sig. = 0.000, which means the multiple linear regression model is suitable for the data set and usable. Durbin-Watson is also suitable while $1 < 1.484 < 2$, which represents there is no correlation between variables in the model. In addition, VIF results all the numbers are less than 2, so no collinearity occurs. The adjusted R square is 0.303, which indicates the independent factors just explain 30.3 % of the change in the dependent variable. The variable X2 has Sig. = 0.500 > 0.000, so the independent variable X2 is excluded from the model. The remaining variables are X1, X3 with Sig. less than 0.05, which has explanatory significance for the model, will be kept. So the standardised regression equation: $Y = 1.097 + 0.345X1 + 0.289X3$.

Test relationship between business information and selection transport enterprises

Table 8

ANOVA Test for Business Type Variable

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	3.371	2	1.686	3.043	.050
Within Groups	92.512	167	.554		
Total	95.883	169			

For the factor type of business, the result shows that the Sig. = 0.50, which is equal to the significance level 50%, then, there are the differences between joint stock companies, limited liability companies, and private enterprises in the decision of selecting transport enterprises.

Table 9

ANOVA Test for Number of Employees Variable

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.680	2	.340	.597	.552
Within Groups	95.203	167	.570		
Total	95.883	169			

As the result of the factor number of employees, the Sig. = 0.552, which is higher than the significance level 50%, which represents the

number of employees factor has no impact on the choice of transport companies.

Table 10

ANOVA Test for Frequency of Transaction Variable

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.561	2	.280	.491	.613
Within Groups	95.322	167	.571		
Total	95.883	169			

Doing one-way ANOVA on the factor frequency of transaction shows that Sig. = 0.613 > 0.05, which also means that the time that the import-

export businesses cooperate with the transport enterprise has no influence on their decision.

Table 11

ANOVA Test for Types of Export Goods Variable

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	7.082	5	1.416	1.769	.122
Within Groups	131.295	164	.801		
Total	138.376	169			

The result in types of export goods is Sig. = 0.122 < 0.5. It means that different export goods will lead to different choices of transport businesses. It makes sense that whether the product the business wants to transport, the transport company can meet it to ship or not.

methods and quantitative research methods, then use IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 tool to help handle the data. As the result of ANOVA and regression, the authors have identified 2 factors: Relationship and Strength have an effect on the choice of transport enterprises in case of import-export enterprises in Da Nang. In which, the factor Relationship has a stronger impact than Strength. Furthermore, the type of export

Discussion

The authors have used both qualitative

goods factor is the criteria that affects the decision to choose the transport enterprises. According to the results, the authors will give the recommendation below.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The study has figured out two factors that have a positive effect on the choice of transport enterprises of import-export companies in Danang. Based on the articles, surveys, and previous research papers, the study has synthesised a total 17 items that may impact on the selection carrier enterprises of the import-export companies. After analysing with the help of SPSS, there are only two factors left (Relationship & Strength) with a total 9 independent variables. In addition, the research also makes the suggestions for both carrier enterprises and import-export companies based on the two left variables and the relationship between business information and selection transport enterprises. Since this study is just focusing on the Danang city, the future research can expand the scale into the other regions of Vietnam and try to develop the other factors that may affect this topic.

Recommendation

Solution for building the relationship with the transport enterprises:

- The businesses can use win-win strategy to allow both parties to gain the values from the contract. It's important that both parties are satisfied with the contract and go for a long-term relationship.
- The discount or any flexibility during the time two parties corporate may also help them create a good relationship and trust for further cooperation.
- Beside the business between two companies, they should also create a personal relationship like friends, which can help them understand the other.

Solution for the strength of transport enterprises

- The transport enterprises should increase or improve their inner capacity for the higher chance of being selected by the import-export enterprises.
- The more the ability of transport enterprises to be flexible on their rates, the more chance they can meet up with the need of the import-export enterprises.

Solution for types of export goods

- The carrier companies should expand their capacity on shipping multiple types of products, which can help create a competitive advantage with the other transport companies.
- Ensuring the shipping ability or handling the problems are needed when the business can ship multiple types of goods.

Competing Interests

The author did not declare any competing interest.

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